

TOOLKIT FOR THE PLANNING OF THE IMPACT MEASUREMENT IN THE EUROPEAN VOLUNTEERING CAPITAL COMPETITION

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Introduction

The European Volunteer Capital Competition is an annual initiative organised by the Centre for European Volunteering (CEV), co-financed by the EU Citizen, Equality, Rights and Values Programme of the EU (CERV). Its aim is to recognise and reward European municipalities for promoting and supporting volunteering and serve as a source of inspiration and motivation for all municipalities across Europe to make even greater efforts in promoting and celebrating volunteering. How is it possible however to **know the value of participation** in this competition, and how can the impact it brings to different stakeholders engaged in the process, communities, and broader society **be measured**? How can the way in which engaging with this award process helps the development of volunteering in a particular municipality, region or country **be demonstrated**? The answers to these questions are possible only if a standardised and comparative evaluation of the activities connected with candidating for the title and its implementation is conducted.

This toolkit contains guidance for the possible approaches and concrete steps to measure the impact of the European Volunteering Capital Competition as required by the Competition rules. It is dedicated to the municipalities planning to be engaged in the competition process to help them develop an evaluation plan that will be most suited to their needs and context. The evaluation plan is a mandatory part of the application. It is designed to help **identify and highlight the changes** that participation in the competition brings to communities.

Evaluation values something. It determines the significance or quality of the programme or activity results. Properly implementing a process that assesses the competition's impact will help show the effect of participation and allow the Centre for European Volunteering (CEV) as the competition organisers, as well as the municipalities and other stakeholders involved, such as local and regional volunteer centres to make critical decisions about the future of volunteering.

A carefully planned evaluation process is essential for its success. Developing a plan upfront guarantees having all the necessary and relevant data, avoiding the need for additional time to sift through superfluous information. Knowing in advance what to evaluate also aids in selecting the most appropriate tools for approach to the assessment.

The toolkit is designed to support the implementation of the European Volunteering Capital Competition measurement methodology that was developed in 2024 based on consultations with previous winners, candidates, CEV Board Members, and staff.

1. About the European Volunteering Capital

The first European Volunteering Capital title was awarded in 2014. Since then, the competition has become one of CEV's central flagship initiatives. It shows the potential of volunteering development at the local level and connects present and future local volunteering actions, strategies, policies, and programmes to the European Context.

The competition **aims to promote volunteering at the local level** and connect it to the European context. It enables volunteers, volunteer-involving and volunteer infrastructure organisations to collaborate more closely with local policymakers in a common cause to strengthen, inspire and celebrate volunteers in their area. It is set up to **recognise and reward** municipalities that support volunteers and volunteering in their communities. It should also serve as a **source of inspiration and motivation** for European municipalities to make even greater efforts to promote and celebrate volunteering.

Participation as a candidate requires a detailed analysis and assessment ('Audit') of volunteer provision at the local level, therefore helping to identify strengths and weaknesses of the approaches taken and acting as a catalyst for improvements. Participation enables stakeholders from different fields and sectors to come together and further develop their local volunteering policy and practice frameworks and strategies, using European standards as guidelines. It also assists the development of volunteering and solidarity in Europe more widely as the examples shared to inspire others across Europe. Finally, joining the competition as a candidate municipality provides the opportunity to join a unique community of practice of municipalities 'European Volunteer Capital Candidates Community' (EVCCC) (and other levels of local and regional authorities) that have expertise in and a shared concern for, strengthening, inspiring and celebrating volunteering and solidarity.

2. Why measure the impact of the European Volunteering Capital Competition

Evaluating the impact of the European Capital Volunteering Competition is crucial to ensure that the competition is accessible, sustainable, and beneficial for all stakeholders involved:

- **Accountability:** Evaluation holds the competition accountable for its objectives. It helps ensure that the resources invested, including time, money, and human capital, are used effectively to benefit the participating municipalities and their communities.
- **Quality Assurance:** Evaluation serves as a quality assurance mechanism for the competition. It ensures that the initiatives promoted through the competition meet established standards and deliver meaningful benefits to the communities involved.
- **Effectiveness Assessment:** Evaluation helps determine whether the volunteering activities and initiatives fostered by the competition achieve their intended outcomes.

- **Continuous Improvement:** Evaluation lets organisers identify strengths and weaknesses in the competition's implementation. This will help make necessary adjustments and improvements to enhance its impact over time.
- **Sustainability:** Understanding the competition's impact is essential for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the initiative, including attracting additional co-financing from sponsors and other funders. If communities perceive little or no benefit, they may be less likely to support or engage with future volunteering efforts in general in the future.
- **Community Engagement and Reciprocity:** An evaluation process can involve community members in assessing the competition's impact, fostering greater community engagement and ownership of the initiatives. Evaluation helps ensure that the competition remains mutually beneficial for all stakeholders.
- **Long-Term Relationships:** Building trust and positive relationships between the competition organisers, participating municipalities, and communities is essential. Evaluation can strengthen these relationships by demonstrating a commitment to accountability and continuous improvement.
- **Policy Development:** Evaluation data can inform the development of policies and guidelines for future competition editions, ensuring that they continue to evolve and contribute to promoting and implementing European rights, equality, and values.
- **Research and Documentation:** Evaluation generates data and evidence that can be used in research and advocacy efforts, contributing to the broader understanding of volunteering and its impact.
- **Visibility:** Evaluation can increase the competition's visibility by promoting the assessment findings, highlighting successes, and encouraging broader participation.
- **Motivation:** Impact evaluation of the competition can motivate existing volunteers, community partners, and participating municipalities while attracting new participants and supporters.
- **Inspiration:** Good practices and extraordinary achievements can inspire other municipalities to focus on goals or indicators that were not considered before.

2. Impact measurement plan as a part of the application process

Since 2013, municipalities of any size from a Council of Europe member state can apply for the title European Volunteering Capital. Currently, applicant municipalities are required to demonstrate their strategies, policies, and programmes in connection to the Blueprint for European Volunteering 2030 and the CEV Volunteering Policy Statements. Evidence about their engagement with and support for the European Solidarity Corps when the applicant comes from an EU member state is also required. Applicants are also asked to indicate if they are signatories of the Integrating Cities Charter.

From 2025, applications consist of:

→ **an online application form with:**

- Specific questions focusing on *current performance and existing practice around volunteering* (worth 70% of the total score for the written part)
- **Impact measurement plan** (worth 20% of the total score for the written part). NB: the space to elaborate the details of the plan is in the online application form.
- An attachment of a maximum of four sides of A4 to describe the *municipality's "Strategy for future growth as concerns the access to, and impact of, quality volunteering, and the legacy of the EV Capital title for volunteers and solidarity locally, nationally and on a European level"* (worth 10% of the total score for the written part)

→ **a video of a maximum of 5 minutes** demonstrating volunteering in the municipality and how it is encouraged and supported, and a physical presentation in Brussels. The video should contribute to showing in a visual way how volunteering policies and programmes are implemented in the municipality. It should provide complementary information to that provided in the application form and during the physical presentation but also be understandable in isolation, keeping in mind that it will be shared online.

Although the distribution of scores indicates that the most critical aspect remains what the municipality has achieved so far and is currently doing, in evaluating applications, we have strengthened the assessment of existing and future plans and objectives by verifying how the planned changes will be monitored and their impact tracked.

Embedding impact measurement and evaluation into the jury evaluation process for European Volunteering Capital candidates aims at providing a more comprehensive overview on the changes brought about by engagement in the competition and the European Volunteering Capital Candidates Community (EVCCC). The impact measurement should provide valuable data to the Municipality and other stakeholders that contributes to the evidence base concerning the benefits of the effort invested in the competition and EVCCC activities.

3. Impact measurement and evaluation theory

In assessing the impact, we can distinguish between monitoring and evaluation.

Monitoring describes collecting the facts and figures related to programs and activities focused on volunteering support and development in the Municipality.

Evaluation is using your collected information to answer questions about how well the volunteering in your Municipality is doing, identify gaps and improvements you can make, and demonstrate your outcomes and impact. e.g., the difference that involving volunteers makes or the added value that involving volunteers brings to the community. It will analyse monitoring information, feedback, case studies, and collected experiences.

Monitoring information describes what has happened. Evaluation is one step further –making a value judgement based on this descriptive information – is the impact good enough? Is it worth the resources we put into the strategy and accompanying policies and programmes?

3.1. Formative and summative evaluation

There are two general approaches to the evaluation: **formative evaluation** and **summative evaluation**. See Table 1.

Table 1 Comparison between formative and summative evaluation

	Formative evaluation	Summative evaluation
Aim	Development of the activities	Support the decision about the future of activities
Purpose	Give feedback for the improvement of the activities (if there are many ideas on how we can improve the intervention, it doesn't mean it is an intervention of low quality; the formative evaluation is not focused on the usefulness of the intervention) Correspondence between what is planned and what is done	Give the information based on which we decide about the activities
Questions	What works? What do we need to improve? How can we improve?	What are the results/outcomes? In which conditions do we reach the outcomes? What are the costs?

Formative evaluation

The formative evaluation provides an increased understanding of the support and development of volunteering in a specific Municipality. The role of formative assessment may differ for the initial stages of program implementation and a long-standing volunteering program or strategy. Indeed, in the case of a new programme, the role of formative evaluation is quite crucial. It brings significant benefits and considerable added value to all the staff involved, as the early identification of any shortcomings allows for their early correction and minimisation of negative impacts. The importance of formative evaluation in longer-term programmes may be that it provides early and relatively easy adaptation to changing conditions (such as the need to adapt to a situation during a pandemic).

Examples of the questions for the formative evaluation:

1. How do you see the volunteer strategy/program implementation until now in your Municipality?
2. What works?

3. What doesn't work?
4. What do you think should be improved?
5. How do you think we can improve?

Summative evaluation

Summative evaluation is used when assessing the results and deciding whether to continue or discontinue the activities focused on volunteer development or support in the Municipality. In this case, the evaluation aims not to look for suggestions for improvement but to state and certify the achievement or non-achievement of the set objectives.

3.2. Process and effects evaluation

According to the subject of the evaluation, a distinction is made between **process** and **effects evaluation**.

Process evaluation

Process evaluation focuses on how a given intervention, in our case, volunteer strategy, is implemented in a particular organisation. It can focus on the context (context evaluation) or the implementation itself (implementation evaluation). Context evaluation looks at how the context influences volunteering and identifies what helps or hinders the implementation of volunteer strategy. Implementation evaluation focuses on how volunteering is developed in the concrete Municipality.

Effects evaluation

The effects evaluation (also results or outcomes evaluation) is focused primarily on describing, exploring, and determining changes in the target group or other stakeholders due to the intervention (Fitzpatrick, Sander, Worthen, 2004). The primary purpose of this evaluation is to analyse changes in the target group's behaviour after their participants were exposed to the intervention. In our case, the effects evaluation is focused on the effects that the EVC award brings to the different stakeholders in the Awarded municipality—that is, the effects on the local/regional/national level.

3.3. Explanation of concepts in the evaluation

Concept	Explanation	Examples
Inputs	<p>Defines all the municipality's resources devoted to EV Capital title and volunteering strategy implementation.</p> <p>Resources can be financial, but also the time of staff, spaces etc</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → number of staff members and volunteers involved in activities connected with the EV Capital title implementation → number of hours spent by staff and volunteers involved in activities connected with the EV Capital title implementation → equipment and materials used during EV Capital title implementation → technology needed for EV Capital title implementation → financial sources needed for EV Capital title implementation
Outputs	<p>Direct elements produced or generated during the EV Capital title.</p> <p>Outputs are measurable and determined accomplishments of EV Capital title.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → number and type of activities within the EV Capital title → number of participants in activities within the EV Capital title implementation → number of partners involved in the development and implementation of the volunteering strategy → number of materials produced thanks to the EVC title
Outcomes	<p>Refer to the EV Capital competition benefits generated in a defined period, usually after EV Capital competition implementation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → number of satisfied beneficiaries → number of new volunteers from specific groups → raised awareness about volunteering and connection to EU values → new connections and networks → increased number of social contacts → increased access to local services

Impact	Changes induced by the EV Capital candidacy and title in the municipality/region/country over extended periods.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → visibility increase of volunteer-involving organizations in the local community → the improvement of the services for volunteers → reduced social isolation
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Understanding the expected impact and clearly defining the difference you want to generate as an EV Capital is not always easy. Still, it is mandatory to have a controlled and predictable process that, in time, will consolidate your role in the local community.

The EV Capital competition impact evaluation should use a combination of “summative” and “formative” assessment and, in connection with the set-up objectives for EV Capital competition in specific municipalities, implement “effects evaluation”.

3.4. Impact evaluation as a process

Impact evaluation is a process that consists of several steps. Based on the literature about evaluation and measuring the impact (the effect of your activities), we offer a list of simple steps to guide you. We will briefly explain each step and, later in a separate chapter, guide you with the planning and designing of the evaluation. See the process in the picture.

6 Steps in impact evaluation

1. Planning and designing the evaluation

The first step in the evaluation process is planning the evaluation. You should have a plan for measuring the effect in various stages. It is essential to keep the competition timeline in mind and adapt the planning to its phases, ensuring the municipality can present impact measurement results at the required moments. For the planning process, please see Chapter 5.

2. Collecting the data

After establishing a suitable design for your evaluation, you must collect the relevant data. You should only collect information and data that is necessary and relevant. You can also use existing data and information where available and valuable.

One way to collect data is to involve the organisations collaborating with you on implementing some of the activities that are necessary for the data collection process. It will be essential to create a system for these partners to report the agreed-upon information about the activities regularly. This way, you can continuously obtain information on the number of volunteers involved, their profiles, their motivation, volunteer hours, beneficiaries, impact and more. The <https://volunteeringimpact.eu/> tool is a free to use option designed by CEV and other partners and can be useful for this purpose and it is important to note that CEV advocates for a "beyond GDP" approach to measuring the value of volunteering.

You can also use your capacities or order a service from an agency or university to collect the needed data.

Even if you plan the impact measurement in detail, there may be some unexpected outcomes. Do not forget to ask your partners about these. You might be surprised by information regarding the involvement of a specific group or newly formed partnerships.

3. Analysing and reviewing collected data

All the data collected within the previous stage of the process needs to be put together and analysed to extract the relevant information and conclusions from it. Collected data can be expressed in numbers (quantitative) or words (qualitative). Each type of data requires a slightly different approach to analysis.

4. Concluding and recommendations

You may need to write up your conclusions based on the evidence you have found. When interpreting information, consider if there are any other possible explanations for your findings. Once you have identified any gaps between results and targets, you can focus on improving. The approach needs to be realistic, specific, and achievable.

5. Communicating the results of impact evaluation

To make sure you get the best possible value from all the efforts that you, stakeholders, and participants have put into the process, think through how the process and results will be communicated amongst those who have taken part, stakeholders, other organisations, groups and funders who could learn from what you have discovered. You may find that the information you have collected, the results and what you have learned during the process have a range of uses – this can be in addition to the primary purpose identified at the beginning. Finally, it is best practice to gather feedback and record what worked well, and what you would do differently next time.

6. Learning from the evaluation

In the final step, you should actively use the findings from your evaluation to learn what is working well and identify areas that need to be improved. They can also be used in a broader perspective. The experience of former EV Capital candidates and winners shows that regular promotion and impact measurement results can lead to new and improved local government policies. They have shared that it is crucial to communicate the impact of the EV Capital competition involvement as it can result in European, National, Regional and local authorities/ policymakers focusing more on volunteering and their role in enabling it to thrive.

4. EV Capital impact measurement plan - Step by step

While planning, it is essential to remember that the application requires the impact measurement plan to be divided into four stages based on the competition cycle. Each period should contain expected outputs and outcomes (indicators) aligned with set goals. It does not mean you should choose different indicators for each stage. You should use the same indicators to show progress throughout the various stages depending on your advancement in the competition.

The timeline for the call for Candidates to be the EV Capital 202 is in the table below.

	From the decision to apply to the presentation of the candidacy	From the presentation of the nomination to the opening ceremony	From the opening ceremony to the closing ceremony	The year after
Period of measuring	02/2025 – 10/2025	10/2025 – 01/2027	01/2027 – 12/2027	01/2028 – 06/2028
When the results of the impact measurement should be presented.	10/2025	02/2027	12/2027	07/2028

The impact measurement plan should include answers to these seven questions as part of the application process. See the picture.

4.1. Define the objectives of your EV Capital candidacy

- What are the general objectives of your municipality in connection with the candidacy?
- What do you want to achieve or improve as a European Volunteer Capital?
- How are these objectives connected with the current situation in the municipality?

You have to define at **least four goals** by choosing from the seven preset goals.

Goal 1 is mandatory.

	To further strengthen the infrastructure of volunteering and cross-sector and cross-field cooperation and collaboration in the European context.	mandatory
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Then, you have to choose at least one goal from the numbers 2 & 3, 4 & 5, and 6 & 7; that's three goals altogether.

goal 2	To strengthen awareness and recognition of the value of volunteering & connection to EU Values.	To choose one
goal 3	To enhance the European dimension of volunteering	
goal 4	To increase the level of understanding and knowledge about volunteering	To choose one
goal 5	To demonstrate the benefits of volunteering for individuals & the local community	
goal 6	To extend the outreach to and involve more people in volunteering in more diverse contexts	To choose one
goal 7	To increase the level of inclusion in volunteering	

Besides that, you can set some additional goals based on your other needs.

The most common goals of former EV Capitals were raising awareness and recognition of volunteering and its connection to EU values, engaging a more significant number and diversity of people in volunteering, focusing on volunteering to enable policy changes, building infrastructure for volunteering, and investing in volunteering.

4.2. Define the focus of the assessment

- What do you want to assess, and which groups do you want to focus on?

After setting up the objectives of EV Capital's candidacy, it is essential to identify and prioritise the target groups and what your municipality wants to evaluate. The assessment models offered in the previous chapter can help answer this question and organise the assessment. The target groups and stakeholders affected by the EV Capital title should be

mentioned. Your municipality can focus on volunteers, partner organisations, beneficiaries, communities, stakeholders, or a Municipality in measuring the impact.

4.3. Select indicators and data

- Which indicators will you use to show the progress and achievements?
- What data do you need to analyse?

The plan should include at least four goals and four indicators. You should select **at least one of the indicators associated with goal number 1** and choose **at least one goal and at least one associated indicator from numbers 2 & 3, 4 & 5, and 6 & 7**. You should also gather and interpret **gender & age aggregated data**.

No	Goal	Indicators
1	To further strengthen the infrastructure of volunteering and cross-sector and cross-field cooperation and collaboration in the European context.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Number of new or improved policies/ strategies/ administrative frameworks (eg departments) adopted by the municipality b. Number of new volunteer centres established / supported c. Number of new partnerships established between the municipality and non-governmental organisations d. Number of new partnerships established between the municipality and for profit employers in volunteering related issues
2	To strengthen awareness and recognition of the value of volunteering & connection to EU Values.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. % change of volunteer related media outputs with references to EU values b. % change of public investment in promotion of volunteering & EU values c. % change of level of perception and / or recognition of the value of volunteering among citizens d. % change of number of specific events and / or initiatives organised to support awareness and recognition of the value of volunteering & connection to EU Value
3	To enhance the European dimension of volunteering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Number of events and activities organised that have a European component b. Number of attendees from other European countries at volunteering events c. Number of engagements at volunteering-related events in other countries d. Number of newly established partnerships with volunteering-related entities in other countries from the public and/ or private sector
4	To increase the level of understanding and knowledge about volunteering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. % change in the number of partnerships with research institutions on volunteering-related matters b. Increase in the variety of type of data collected about volunteering

		<p>c. Development of the process of long-term, regular and comparable data collection about volunteering</p> <p>d. Increase in capacity to measure the economic and social value</p>
5	To demonstrate the benefits of volunteering on individuals & the local community	<p>% change in level of perceived well-being of volunteers amongst volunteers</p> <p>b. % change in level of perceived sense of inclusion in the local community for volunteers</p> <p>c. % change in level of perceived inclusion as part of the European Union for volunteers</p> <p>d. Increase in opportunities for volunteers to certify and have recognised skills and competencies acquired whilst volunteering</p>
6	To extend the outreach to and involve more people in volunteering in more diverse contexts	<p>% change in number of volunteers of different genders and with disabilities and / or people of migrant backgrounds/ Roma and other marginalised groups etc</p> <p>b. % change in number volunteer hours / activities in the municipality</p> <p>c. Number and quality of developed / adopted/improved mechanisms for matching volunteers with opportunities</p> <p>d. % change in number, variety and diversity of types of activities / areas covered by volunteers</p>
7	To increase the level of inclusion in volunteering	<p>a. % change of number of volunteer programmes involving people with disabilities and / or people of migrant backgrounds / Roma and other marginalised groups etc</p> <p>b. % change of number of volunteer coordinators, managers and policy makers with inclusive volunteering training</p> <p>c. % change of perceived inclusiveness in volunteer organisations</p> <p>d. % change of perceived inclusiveness in volunteering among people with fewer opportunities / from marginalised groups</p>

You can use two types of data: quantitative (outputs or “hard”) data and qualitative (outcomes or “soft”) data. **A good evaluation uses quantitative and qualitative measures to present a complete picture of the impact.**

Quantitative Data

“Quantitative” data describes information in numbers. There is a variety of data you can obtain, such as:

- Number and type of organisations working with volunteers
- Number of volunteers involved in one-time activities
- Number of long-term volunteers
- Number of clients/ beneficiaries served by volunteers
- Number of volunteer hours donated
- Economic value of volunteers’ hours
- Number of professionals supporting volunteers
- Number of new activities/events organised
- Number of new policies

Qualitative Data

Many aspects of impact cannot be easily quantified. This is referred to as “qualitative” data. These include the more intangible benefits or outcomes, for example, increased awareness of EU values, increased understanding of Fundamental Values and the Rule of Law, increased beneficiaries’ satisfaction, improved well-being, and increased community involvement. Qualitative data are contained in narrative accounts, interviews, observations, testimonials and organisational reports. This “soft” data will probably play a more significant role in your evaluation process than “hard” data, although facts and figures are essential too.

Qualitative data is more sensitive to planning. Previous EV Capital candidates and winners that were not well-prepared for impact measurement reported that their ability to obtain qualitative data was very low, and they based their conclusions solely on quantitative data.

4.4. Define approach and tools for impact measurement

- **How will you assess the EV Capital Competition impact?**
- **What are the methods and tools you will use?**

There are two common ways of measuring the impact:

- **Before and after** (sometimes called “pre and post-test”). This is an excellent approach if you can plan to measure impact before the group experiencing impacts begins the activity. For example, if you want to find out the impact of activities on skills or the well-being of the volunteers, you could ask them a suite of questions before they are involved in the activities (pre) and **again** after they have been involved for a while (post). Then, you can look at their responses' differences to measure what change had happened. If you use this approach, think about the **likely** impact timing. Some impacts might be immediate, others mid or long-term. Plan when you would collect data accordingly.

→ **Retrospective or post-test.** Unless we are very good at planning “ahead” for measuring impact, you often need to measure it after an activity has started. In this case, you need to ask whether they feel they have changed due to the volunteering activities after or during the activity. For example, you could ask beneficiaries whether their skills or well-being - have increased due to participation in activities. Or suppose you aim to increase knowledge about voluntary organisations in your Municipality. In that case, you can ask your citizens whether they gained more information about **volunteering** in the Municipality over the past year. This approach is not considered as robust or reliable as the before-and-after, but it is often the only option for assessing the impact.

This approach is recommended not only for qualitative data. For example, if you aim to increase the number of volunteers, you should have some baseline numbers gathered in advance that can be used for comparison when later data is obtained.

Planning data collection in cooperation with your partners can also be helpful for them. Once they begin collecting data for you, they may also find it valuable for their purposes. This could serve as a starting point for their internal evaluation, which could, in turn, impact the quality of the volunteering opportunities and services they provide.

There are **several methods and tools** for impact assessment. Although there are practical advantages and disadvantages to different methods, the choice of method must be driven primarily by the question you want to answer. However, you should also consider practicalities – plan how the data will be analysed once collected. It is not good practice to ask people to give up their time and personal information if you cannot process and use what they provide, so ensure you can analyse the data you receive.

To design an adapted approach to measuring EV Capital Competition impact within your municipality, it is crucial to consider a set of criteria that will help you tailor the design according to its aim and institutional profile. The most important criteria to have in mind are:

- *Comparability* – make sure you are capturing the same phenomenon/aspects in the same way, in different moments
- *Feasibility* - ensure that all the assessments can occur in a specific place and time. Focus your efforts on what is possible.
- *Cost-effectiveness* - ensure that the resources you invest in the assessment are proportionate to the results you achieve. When determining satisfaction, a short game or form might be enough, so you will not use an extensive interview with each participant to measure it.
- *Efficiency* - maximise your results and minimise the resource investment of all types. You might be able to use one method or tool to reach more than one desired result.
- *Reliability* - ensuring that the process can yield reliable results. For the results to be valuable, you must ensure the process is transparent and can be trusted. Even at a closer look, there should be no questions about whether your final assessment reflects reality. ([ILO, 2011](#))

You can use:

- Questionnaires for citizens, community partners, service beneficiaries, volunteers, community members or other stakeholders;
- Observation;
- Interviews;
- Focus Groups;
- Reports.

4.5. Plan stakeholders involvement

- **Describe which entities you have been involved with and plan to be involved after receiving the title.**
- **Who was involved in preparing the impact measurement plan for this application?**
- **Who will manage the implementation of the plan?**
- **Who do you expect will provide the necessary data for the evaluation?**

The success of impact measurement depends on the willingness and readiness of the most suitable stakeholders to participate in its preparation and implementation.

For example, if you chose goal number 6 and its indicator, “quality of developed / adopted / improved mechanisms for matching volunteers with opportunities”. In that case, you will probably need to ask new volunteers and coordinators in the organisations, not the beneficiaries or any employees of the volunteer organisation. If you want to understand the change of perceived inclusiveness in volunteer organisations (indicators connected with goal number 7), you can collect your data from staff.

A vital issue in engaging anyone in assessment is respecting their time, obligations, and resources. Discussing your ideas regarding impact evaluation with those with the data you need might be crucial. You can avoid making them feel uninvolved and used and thus unwilling to share the data. If you need data about the number of volunteers involved in activities, explain why it is essential, how you will use that data and what benefit it will bring to organisations, communities or society. Consider the easiest way to collect them, considering the capacities and abilities of those who should participate.

4.6. Plan resources you need for impact measurement implementation

- **What resources do you have (time, staff, money, facilities, and equipment)?**
- **Are the necessary resources available (time, staff, money, facilities, and equipment) to measure the impact?**
- **Who can be involved in the process, and what skills can they offer?**

Be aware that impact assessment requires some investment. Depending on the way of data collection, you should take into consideration the resources that you have available for the entire process:

- **Time.** What is the allocated time for implementing the assessment? Are there any limitations (deadlines, events, etc.)?

Experienced EV Capital candidates and winners recommend starting as soon as the decision to be a candidate or even consider to be a candidate is made. Even if you do not receive the title, it is reasonable to assume that your goals are important to you, and at least some of them can be achieved regardless of the competition's outcome. The established process and the data collected will make this easier for you.

→ **People.** Who can be involved in the process, and what skills can they offer? Who will collect the data?

Avoid having the planning and creation of the application content handled solely by municipality professionals. Instead, create partnerships that can strengthen your capacities throughout the process.

An NGO may initiate interest in participating in the EV Capital Competition and take on the role of leader in the preparation process. In such a case, collaboration between the Municipality and the initiator becomes even more critical, and the goals should be set jointly to ensure they are achieved in the future.

Most municipalities do not have their research experts. It is recommended that they establish a partnership with an institution with expertise in the research field, such as a university. There can be even more institutions working on different tasks.

→ **Money.** What are the costs for the assessment (printings, working hours for staff members, travel costs for participants, etc.) and the budget limitations?

Remember to calculate expenses on external capacities. If you want to involve a research institution or an agency, this will probably relate to some expenses.

→ **Facilities and equipment.** What specific resources might you need (recorder, microphone, etc.)?

4.7. Consider ethical issues connected with the impact assessment

→ **What ethical issues are connected with assessing the impact, and how will you ensure the respect of the moral rules of your impact evaluation?**

In the evaluation process, you should also address the ethical issues of your assessment, not only when it comes to involving certain at-risk groups. Considering the implications of your evaluation's conclusions should be part of any research that involves people and their actions. The ethical principles of evaluation are formulated in general terms; their specific application is always a matter for the person responsible for the evaluation.

The key things to remember are whether your participants have given *full informed consent* agreeing to participate in the evaluation with full knowledge of the assessment and how it will be used. You must consider *anonymity* when reporting the evaluation results, not revealing the identity of someone whose words you use in the reports or presentations. Anonymity is critical when participants are encouraged to give honest feedback on something or talk about personal issues. Another rule is to secure *confidentiality*, meaning the data will only be available to a limited set of named individuals. You also need to ensure that you are in line with the *General Data Protection Rules* that provide clear guidelines on how to deal with and store the information. You may

not need to collect personal data in your assessment, but you must keep the information secure if you do so.

If you plan to use the evaluation data for research purposes or publish it in a research paper, remember to ask for the approval of the responsible body, such as the ethical committee, at your institution before you start collecting the data.

4.8. Plan the impact measurement timeline

→ **What will be the indicators that you will measure and show in the different stages?**

→ **First stage: From the decision to apply to the candidacy presentation.** You are expected to present the results of the first impact measurement step covering the application preparation stage. These could be numbers or other successes achieved during this period or the results of mapping that will be used to compare with the results of EV Capital activities in “before and after” testing.

→ **Second stage: From the presentation of the candidacy to the opening ceremony of EV Capital,** you are expected to present the results of the preparation stage for EV Capital.

→ **Third stage: From the opening ceremony to the closing ceremony.** The impact should be the most significant in the year of being EV Capital.

→ **Fourth stage: After one year as EV Capital,** the municipality is expected to use the legacy of the title to develop the volunteer environment further. The municipality should also plan its impact after this period.

5. Criteria for the evaluation of the impact measurement plan

Jury members will assess your impact evaluation plan based on several criteria. Before you apply, you can use these criteria as a self-evaluation tool.

Criteria		Self-evaluation questions	Yes/No/It can be improved.
Contextual sensitivity	Your impact measurement plan should reflect your unique cultural, social, and economic contexts. It should recognise and respect local traditions, values, and practices. Since the objectives of the EV Capital Competition implementation differ in each Municipality, the	Is the impact measurement plan contextual? Is it connected to the current performance and practices around volunteering described in the first	

	evaluation model should be adapted for your municipality.	part of the application?	
Inclusivity and stakeholder engagement	Various stakeholders, including community members, volunteers, local governments, non-profits, and other relevant entities, prepared and implemented the measurement plan.	Are different stakeholders involved in the impact measurement plan and its implementation?	
Clear objectives and indicators	The plan should establish clear, measurable goals for what the competition aims to achieve in your municipality.	Are the clear objectives and indicators defined? Are they connected? Is the combination of qualitative and quantitative data used?	
Appropriate model and tools and evidence-based approach	You should define the appropriate model and tools for assessing the impact, considering the purpose of the work, why you are evaluating the effect, and available resources. You should implement an evidence-based approach to the evaluation, using qualitative and quantitative methods to understand the competition's impact comprehensively. Credible data sources and reliable evaluation tools to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings should be described.	Is it clear how you will assess the EVC impact? Are the methods and tools defined? Is the methodology appropriate to measure the indicators? Are resources defined? Is the approach evidence-based?	
Timeline, adaptability, and continuous improvement	The impact measurement plan should be adaptable, allowing adjustments to new insights, challenges, or changes in the competition's scope. The plan also proposes how the evaluation findings will be used for continuous improvement. The timeline for different stages of EVCC is prepared.	Is the timeline for different stages prepared? Is the plan adaptable? Is it clear how the results will be used?	
Ethical Considerations	The impact measurement plan should ensure that the evaluation process is conducted ethically, respecting all	Is it clear how you will respect the ethical rules of your impact evaluation?	

	participants' privacy, rights, and dignity.		
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6. Tips to guide your impact evaluation

During the application process

- Involve partners from the non-profit and business sectors in planning. Each can bring their perspective, resources, and expertise.
- Analyse what you already have and where you see the potential for improvement.
- Plan in detail what tools will be used for evaluation.
- Plan your budget wisely. If possible, calculate your expenses and focus on funding your partners' volunteering infrastructure and activities.

During the year of being EV Capital

- Use every opportunity to network on all levels
- Promotion encourages other promotions. If you show the way, the others will follow.
- Unexpected crises can arrive while you are holding the title. It has happened before; EVCs faced pandemics and war. It might need a change of approach, but remember that there are Municipalities you can learn from. Stay in touch with former EV Capital candidates and winners through the EVCCC.

After the year of being EV Capital

- Analyse the impact from a broader perspective. Were there any unexpected outcomes? What is the legacy of the title in your Municipality?
Former EV Capitals reported an unexpected impact: an increased number of strangers in volunteering, increased level of participation in the decision-making process as a result of built infrastructure; the Municipality realised how professional NGOs are, communication with other municipalities in the country was strengthened, change the approach from supporting individual activities to viewing volunteering as a way to enhance solidarity, the business sector started to think about sustainability,...
- Evaluate with your partners and build on good practice.
- Decide what data you can collect regularly and keep using your findings to promote volunteering.

- Besides that, you can recommend your partners start with a simple evaluation of activities like feedback, satisfaction with activities...

References

Fitzpatrick, J. L., Sanders, J., R., Worthen, B. R. (2004). Program Evaluation - Alternative Approaches and Practical Guidelines. Allyn and Bacon.

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